

Legal Threats in Digital Banking Sector

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Mrs.M.Pratheepa, M.Com., M.Phil., M.B.A.,
Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Commerce
Urumu Dhanalakshmi College, Trichy

Dr.A.Selvendran, M.Com., M.Phil., M.B.A., Ph.D.,
Associate Professor, Department of Commerce
Government Arts College, Thuvakudi, Trichy

Abstract

Digital banking has a lot of benefits that add value to customer's satisfaction in term of better service quality, and at the same time enable banks to gain a competitive advantage over other competitors. However, more attention towards digital banking security is required and needed against fraudulent behavior because the lack of control over security makes digital banking still untrusted for many till to day. This paper presents security issues related to digital banking along with the characteristics and challenges of digital banking fraud. Different types of attacks, some fraud detection strategies, and some prevention methods used by electronic banks, are also presented in this paper. An expert opinion method was used to rank different model and techniques in security. Results indicated that the most effective model is "Transaction Monitoring" and the worst models based on respondent's opinions are "Virtual Keyboards", "Browser Protection", and "Device Identification".

Introduction

Electronic finance system aims to provide easy access to banking services for customers. Both banks and customers stand to benefit from the introduction of electronic banking schemes, since the bank can offer its services at much lower cost, while the customer can access the services from any location at any time. Indeed, these benefits can obviate the need for branches or tellers altogether, resulting in the emergence of so called virtual banks, who conduct business purely on an electronic basis.

The transition from a paper-based monetary system to an electronic payments system will reduce transaction costs, expand markets, and empower individuals. The speed of that transition and the expected benefits, however, will depend on creating a legal infrastructure that penalizes failure and rewards success. The rules that govern the new monetary universe will have to be transparent, equally applied, and consistent with individual freedom if people are to have trust and confidence in digital money and digital commerce.

Money is an important commodity to all alike. And all commercial transactions involve money. It is the single thing that all mankind in

interested in the most acute fashion. This is what motivates a person to exert himself and excel himself in his vocations. The assurance that his labour shall be rewarded justly in monetary terms is the crux of all industrious activities. Unless one is a philanthropist with no interest in material benefits.

The traditional dimensions of banking are fast disappearing with the advent of the virtual reality digital banking. Ever since the Internet has facilitated the conduct of transactions and commerce on the Net, the nature of businesses has changed, the banking conditions are changed, the variety of products available is unlimited and the quality of products improved due to stiff competition from rival banking businesses and the services offered by the e-banking unlimited. With this has arisen the problem of the currency in which a transaction is to be conducted the exchange rates that are to be applicable in case of a transaction on-line etc.

The need for digital money is thus justified to indicate that traditional forms of money are unsuited for transactions on the net. Digital cash brings benefits as well as problems. One major advantage of digital cash is its increased efficiency opening new opportunities, especially for small businesses. On the other hand, it will encourage potentially the worsening of problems over taxation and money laundering. In turn, these problems may alter foreign exchange rates, disturb money supplies, and encourage an overall financial crisis.

The transnationality of digital cash - the ability of digital cash to flow freely across national borders - encourages these benefits and problems, and could have significant repercussions internationally. From an economic view, this transnationality is the most important characteristic of digital cash. If digital cash behaved like traditional currencies, circulating within a national border and controlled by a central monetary authority, there would be few economic implications that would be worth analysing. In this scenario, digital cash would be nothing more than a convenient transaction method such as a credit card. Digital cash's very transnationality has the potential to cause conflict between digital space and nation states. If digital cash spreads successfully in the next century, its history may be written as a transcript of economic battles between nation states.

I. Digital Banking in India – Guidelines

India is no stranger to regulation of E-Commerce. As the use of Internet banking increases the necessity for regulation arises. Accordingly RBI has set certain standards for regulation. They are categorized as:

1. Technology and Security Standards
2. Legal Issues
3. Regulatory and Supervisory Issues

As regards Technology issues, the security for transactions conducted on the Net is the main issue. The measures to be adopted by banks are all centred around this point. Having a security policy with an information systems officer and a Information Technology Division with Dual key Encryption for transactions being implemented, data protection, with user ids passwords, smart cards and other biometric technologies, firewalls for databases with a real-time security alert etc are some of the measures suggested for secure Internet Transactions.

From a legal perspective, the existing regulatory framework over banks will be extended to Internet banking also. In India, the Information Technology Act, 2000, in Section 3(2) provides for a particular technology (viz., the asymmetric crypto system and hash function) as a means of authenticating electronic record. Any other method used by banks for authentication should be recognized as a source of legal risk. Under the present regime there is an obligation on banks to maintain secrecy and confidentiality of customers' accounts. In the Internet banking scenario, the risk of banks not meeting the above obligation is high on account of several factors. Despite all

reasonable precautions, banks may be exposed to enhanced risk of liability to customers on account of breach of secrecy, denial of service etc., because of hacking/ other technological failures. The banks should, therefore, institute adequate risk control measures to manage such risks.

II. Regulating Digital Transactions - Impact of Digital Money on Various Agencies

The term ‘digital money’ encompasses stored-value cards based on chips, plus technology based payment mechanisms. It’s set to have substantial impacts on financial services industry, plus flow-on effects on society as a whole. Depending on a whole host of factors, these may be evolutionary, or utterly revolutionary.

Digital money or spendable balances represented solely by digits on a bank’s balance sheet – is not new. Banking historians have found that merchants were making payments by transferring bank account balances back in 1200 AD. It doesn’t really matter whether the digits on the bank’s balance sheet are displayed in ink or in pixels. What has been changing over the centuries is the usual method of authorizing the transfer of balances from one account to another.

Remote, paperless, and instantaneously executed authorization of funds transfer, in the form of “wiring” money from one account to another, has been around at the wholesale level following the introduction of the electric based transaction. What is called nation electronic funds transfer or NEFT, wherein an individual accesses the payment system by means of a debit card reader or a personal computer, basically brings the wiring of money down to the level of the retail transaction.

Payment is the ultimate step in any transaction. A book to be bought, a car to be made, a meal to be served, or a distance to be travelled. All involve this final step of payment. Because everything has a price, and for any transaction to be complete legally this price has to be paid. Of course there are things, which do not have a price and are free for anyone to enjoy, like the sunshine, or the air etc. But these are not subjects of any commerce. Once they enter this sphere they too may have a price. All contracts have the stipulation of a valid consideration for the contract to be complete. This is an indispensable part of a valid contract. Having thus established that payments are a necessary part of everyday commercial transactions, it becomes necessary to recognize the various modes of payments that are in use. There are principally four modes of payments:

- (a) Cash
- (b) Cheque
- (c) Credit Cards
- (d) Electronic Fund Transfers

These are all modes of payments as are prevalent today. For modes of payments to reach this advanced stage, the concept of money and the kinds of money have undergone a series of changes.

III. Legal Threats and Role of RBI - Transition to Digital Currency

At present digital money as a means of exchange is being developed by many firms, banks and governments. Its use is still restricted to market niches and on the Internet an extensive use of it in the near future is foreseeable. The economic consequences of digital cash and its implications from the view of economics. In recent years, several proposals for electronic cash have appeared in digital space are already in use. The economic consequences of these transactions have not yet been fully examined.

To some observers, one important economic consequence of electronic cash is the free issue of private currency by commercial banks or other non-firms. However, if we look at the history of money, it is not easy to make privately issued currency credible in the eyes and wallets of the public. As long as there is competition between banks, private banks will sometimes become bankrupt.

Nothing is more debilitating to the credibility of privately issued currency than bankruptcy. The most important characteristic of digital cash is its transnationality. Digital cash does not recognize national borders. It is not controlled by any central bank of any nation state. The unprecedented efficiency of international payments with digital cash may indeed increase the instability of the global monetary system. This efficiency indeed may lead to conflicts between digital cash providers and users and the central banks of nation states.

IV. The Legal Framework For EFTs

There are many legal issues in electronic transactions but the principal issues which are regarding user confidence in conducting transactions electronically and which could be remedied by appropriate law reform are as follows:

1. Doubts as to the Legal Efficacy of Electronic Records and Electronic Authentication

Preferably, electronic records and electronic authentication should be as effective as written messages and manual signatures, including for contract formation. This means that they should:

- satisfy legal form requirements for writing, signature and originals;
- be admissible in evidence; and
- satisfy statutory record retention requirements.

2. Uncertainty of Application of Existing Legal Rules

This includes the time and place of receipt of electronic messages.

3. Risk of Fraud and Error in Electronic Messages

This is sometimes described as the 'non-repudiation' issue. As in paper-based transactions conducted at a distance, there are risks that a message has not in fact been sent by the apparent sender, that the message may have been altered in transit, and that the apparent sender therefore may repudiate the message, leading to loss if the message has been relied upon by a recipient. The technical management of these risks requires a technical means to reliably authenticate the message sender's identity and the sender's intent to approve or otherwise associate himself or herself with the message content and to guarantee message integrity. The legal allocation of risk of loss caused by unauthorised or altered messages as between the apparent sender and the recipient in paper-based transactions is determined by the general law of agency and, in some cases, by contract between the parties. The same legal mechanisms will operate for electronic transactions and, in some law reform models, are supplemented by new legal rules.

Conclusion

In a country like India, as actuarial trust domains become more differentiated, filling many niches that heretofore could not be envisioned, the total system will still be able to manage these interacting complex identity sets in an efficient manner. Digital certificates, digital signatures, private certificate authorities, and increasingly capable actuarial evaluation and scoring systems will easily manage complexity at lower costs than is possible today.